

Short self-reported sleep duration and suicidal behaviour: a cross-sectional study

Short sleep and suicide

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ABSTRACT

Background: Prior studies on the association between sleep disturbances and suicidal behaviour did not explore whether or not short sleep is a marker of suicide intent, lethality or risk.

Methods: *Design:* Cross-sectional. *Participants:* Suicide attempters (SAs) (n=434). Controls included 83 psychiatric inpatients who have never been SAs, and 509 healthy controls. *Measurements:* Short sleep was defined by self-assessment as \leq 5 hours per day. The MINI and the DSM-IV version of the International Personality Disorder Examination Screening Questionnaire were used to diagnose Axis I and Axis II diagnoses, respectively. Suicide intent and lethality were evaluated through the Beck's Suicidal Intent Scale (SIS) and the Risk-Rescue Rating Scale (RRRS), respectively. Beck's Medical Lethality Scale (BMLS) was administered to assess the degree of medical injury, and the SAD PERSONS mnemonic scale was used to evaluate suicide risk. *Statistical analyses:* Chi-square tests and logistic regression analyses explored frequencies of short sleep in 3 samples. Chi-square tests explored whether or not suicide intent, lethality and risk were greater in SAs with short-sleep versus those without short-sleep.

Results: Short sleep was more prevalent in SAs than in psychiatric controls only in males. In female SAs, short sleep was significantly associated with several SIS items and high scores in the SAD PERSONS.

Limitations: Sleep duration was assessed only by self-report.

Conclusions: The association between short sleep and suicidal behaviour may be partly explained by confounders. Short sleep may be a marker of severity of suicidal behaviour among female SAs.

Key words: Suicidal behaviour, sleep duration, mental disorders, personality, intent, and lethality

Introduction

Suicide is a huge public health problem causing nearly one million deaths worldwide in a given year (Mann et al., 2005). Researchers and clinicians have demonstrated an increasing interest in the association between sleep and suicidal behaviours. A number of studies have documented this association using different measures of sleep disturbances such as nightmares (Bernert et al., 2005; Liu, 2004) and insomnia (Agargun et al., 1997; Carli et al., 2010; McCall et al., 2010; Sjostrom et al., 2007). Indeed, sleep disturbances have been associated with higher mortality (Kripke et al., 2002; Tamakoshi and Ohno, 2004) and suicide rates (Agargun and Besiroglu, 2005; Goldstein et al., 2008; Liu and Buysse, 2006; Nruham et al., 2008; Sabo et al., 1991; Wojnar et al., 2009), even independently of the presence of psychiatric disorders (Agargun and Besiroglu, 2005; Bernert et al., 2005).

Sleep disturbances are common. In the US, 16-25% of the general population manifest them (Wojnar et al., 2009). Sleep disturbances have been associated with risk for a number of medical (Buxton et al., 2010; Cappuccio et al., 2008; Chandola et al., 2010; Stang et al., 2008) and psychiatric disorders (Breslau et al., 1996; Gillin, 1998; Goldstein et al., 2008; Sjostrom et al. 2007). They are incorporated in the diagnostic criteria of several psychiatric disorders including major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder, and generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) (Goodwin and Marusic, 2008).

To date, few studies evaluating the association between suicide and sleep disturbances have used “total sleep time”, a core indicator in clinical sleep medicine and epidemiology sleep research (van den Berg et al., 2008). Goodwin

and Marusic explored the association between sleep duration and suicidal ideation and suicide attempts using data from the National Comorbidity Survey (n = 8098) (Goodwin and Marusic, 2008). Their most interesting finding was that the association between short sleep and suicide attempts did not depend on the presence of mental disorders. Unfortunately, the authors did not address the relationship between sleep duration and severity of suicidal behaviour. Furthermore, previous research in suicide attempters (SAs) has failed to control for associations between sleep duration and sociodemographic characteristics, psychiatric disorders and personality disorders (PDs). In addition, most of these studies on the association between suicide and sleep disturbances have been restricted to patients with mood disorders (Agargun et al., 1997; Fawcett, et al., 1990; Sjostrom et al., 2007), paying little attention to other psychiatric disorders. The severity of suicidal behaviour is usually associated with higher suicide intent, medical lethality, and the use of high-lethality methods (Dejong et al., 2010; Suominen et al., 2004). However, little research has been carried out to explore the relationship between sleep disturbances and suicidal behaviour characteristics such as intent, lethality and risk.

In view of the limitations of previous studies and the need for further study of several issues concerning the association between short sleep duration and suicidal behaviours, the present study sought to: (1) compare after gender stratification the prevalence of short sleep in suicide attempters (SAs) with two types of controls, psychiatric inpatients who have never been SAs and healthy controls; (2) identify clinical variables associated with increased risk for short sleep among SAs; and (3) establish the relationship between short sleep and the severity

and risk of suicide attempts among SAs. In this regard, we propose that short sleep might be a marker of intent, lethality and risk of suicide attempts.

Methods

Samples

Participants were 18 years or older and provided written informed consent before participating in the study. The cases included 434 SAs (289 women and 145 men) admitted to two university hospitals in Madrid, Spain, between 1999 and 2003. The recruitment process has been described in detail elsewhere (Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2009a, b). In short, a research psychiatrist consecutively assessed the first 235 SAs. The remaining non-consecutive evaluations were made by residents in psychiatry with specific training to assess suicide attempts, and close supervision. As assessment conditions were slightly different, some differences could be expected. However, no significant differences were found with regard to either sociodemographic or clinical diagnoses. As previously reported (Diaz et al., 2003), approximately 84% of approached SAs consented to take part in our study. SAs who refused study participation did not significantly differ in demographic variables from study participants. Suicide attempts were defined as "a self-destructive behaviour with intent to end one's life independent of resulting damage" (O'Carroll et al., 1996; Silverman et al., 2007, a, b).

Controls included 83 psychiatric inpatients (52 men and 31 women) who had never been SAs, and 509 healthy controls (201 women and 308 men) from the same hospitals. Psychiatric inpatients were subjects hospitalized for a reason other than suicidal behaviour and without records of suicidal behaviour. We enrolled all consecutive consenting psychiatric inpatients. Healthy controls were recruited

among consecutive consenting blood donors. The General Health Questionnaire-12 (GHQ-12) was used to rule out psychopathology in healthy controls (Goldberg and Williams, 1988). Healthy controls scoring >8 on the GHQ-12 (Castle et al., 2004) or with a history of any Axis I diagnoses, treatments or admissions were excluded. They also lacked first-degree self-reported familial history of mental disorders. The study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the appropriate ethics committee.

Diagnostic assessment

The MINI was used to establish DSM-IV Axis I diagnoses in SAs and psychiatric controls. The MINI is a short and efficient structured diagnostic interview used to assess psychiatric disorders. PDs were assessed according to the DSM-IV version of the International Personality Disorder Examination Screening Questionnaire (IPDE-SQ). This instrument was selected because of its validity, reliability, brevity, and ease of administration (Egan, 2003). In order to increase specificity we used adjusted cut-off points for every PD and generated criteria for diagnosis at a more stringent level (Loranger, 1995). A full description of this strategy is described elsewhere (Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2009a, b; Tyrer, 2009).

Sleep duration

All participants were openly asked about the number of hours they slept daily in the month preceding the assessment with the question, "How many hours did you sleep at night every day in the last month?" As in previous research (Fernandez-Mendoza, et al., 2010; Goodwin and Marusic, 2008; Hasler et al., 2004) sleep duration was dichotomized into short sleep (sleeping ≤ 5 hours) or not. We did not

use sleep items from the MINI diagnoses, in order to avoid biases from diagnosis-specific information.

Suicide scales

Four clinical scales were used to measure suicide intent, lethality, and suicide risk in SAs (Table 1). The Beck's Suicidal Intent Scale (SIS) was used to assess suicide intent (Beck et al., 1974). The Risk-Rescue Rating Scale (RRRS) was administered to assess the lethality of suicide attempts (Misson et al., 2010). The Beck's Medical Lethality Scale (BMLS) was used to evaluate the degree of medical injury secondary to the suicide attempt (Beck et al., 1975; Zalsman et al., 2006). The SAD PERSONS mnemonic scale was used for predicting the need for hospitalization of subjects at risk of suicide (Hockberger and Rothstein, 1988; Patterson et al., 1983). The SAD PERSONS scale can be viewed as a marker of suicide risk.

--please insert **Table 1** about here--

Other clinical scales and sociodemographic factors

Lifetime impulsivity was evaluated with the Spanish version of the Barratt Impulsiveness Scale, version 11 (BIS-11). The BIS-11 contains 30 self-report items (Oquendo et al., 2001). Studied sociodemographic factors included age (18-35, 36-50, 51-65, and >65 years old), gender, working status, and civil state.

Statistical Analyses

Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$. Analyses were conducted using SPSS v17.0. For the first study goal, we compared short-sleep rates between SA patients and psychiatric and healthy controls. Two-sided Chi-square or Fisher exact tests

(FET) were used for significance and odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for effect size. In order to control the effect of mental and personality disorders on sleep duration, we carried out a logistic regression (backward stepwise) in the SA plus psychiatric control samples with short sleep as the dependent variable and gender, age, group (SA vs. psychiatric controls), and main diagnoses (current major depressive episode [MDE], hypomanic episode, alcohol abuse, drug abuse, and PDs) as independent variables. We used the Hosmer and Lemeshow Test for assessing the fitness of the logistic regression models.

For the second goal, studying variables associated with short sleep, we only included SAs. The sample of SAs was divided into those with and without short sleep. Demographic characteristics, lifetime impulsivity and psychiatric disorders and PDs were compared between the two groups. The presence or absence of short sleep was used as a dependent variable, first in univariate analyses and then in logistic regression models using the backward stepwise procedure. Independent variables included gender, age, current MDE, GAD, alcohol use disorders, and the different clusters of PDs, since these variables have been shown to be associated with suicide attempts in our analyses and the literature.

The third goal was studying the association of short sleep and suicide severity and risk (SIS, the RRRS items, BMLS, and SAD PERSONS global scores) among SAs. First, chi-square tests explored whether or not suicide intent, lethality and risk were greater among SAs with short-sleep than among those without short-sleep. Second, a logistic regression (backward stepwise) with SAD PERSONS as the dependent variable and age, gender, short sleep and some of the main diagnoses as independent variables was conducted.

Results

SAs were significantly younger than psychiatric inpatients (mean age \pm SD: 36.6 \pm 14.2 vs. 40.9 \pm 13.2; $p=0.027$). The mean age of healthy controls was 35.8 \pm 12.8 (non-significant difference). With regard to gender, 66% of the SAs were females compared with 63% of the psychiatric controls (non-significant), and 39% of the healthy controls ($p<0.001$). The mean age of female SAs was 34.9 (\pm 13.4), while male SAs were slightly older (36.9 \pm 15.3).

The prevalence of some psychiatric conditions was significantly different in SAs and psychiatric inpatients. SAs were more likely diagnosed with current MDE (57% vs. 39%; $p=0.003$), alcohol abuse (11% vs. 1%; $p=0.003$), and drug dependence (9% vs. 2%; $p=0.045$), among others. Furthermore, SAs showed more frequently at least one PD as measured by the IPDE-SQ than psychiatric inpatient controls (74% vs. 49%; $p<0.001$). A full report with all MINI diagnoses across groups stratified by gender is shown in Table 2.

--please insert **Table 2** about here--

First goal: short sleep in cases and controls

The respective prevalences of short sleep among healthy controls, psychiatric inpatients, and SAs were 9%, 23%, and 37%. Thus, the short sleep risk was two-fold higher in SAs than in psychiatric controls (OR(CI)=2.0(1.1-3.4); Table 3) and five times more likely than in healthy controls (OR(CI)=5.7(4.0-8.1); Table 3). After stratifying by gender, we found that the differences in the rates of short sleep remained higher to a statistically significant degree when comparing SAs and healthy controls but when compared with psychiatric controls, the differences remained significant only in males (Table 3). In the logistic regression model in the

SA plus psychiatric control samples, only current MDE (Wald chi-square=4.99, degrees of freedom, df=1, p= 0.025), and age \geq 65 years (Wald chi-square=24.54, df=1, p< 0.001) significantly increased the likelihood of short sleep.

--please insert **Table 3** about here--

Second goal: studying variables associated with short sleep in SAs

Short sleep duration was significantly associated with older age, male gender, current MDE and GAD in the univariate analyses. In the logistic regression model, current MDE and GAD increased the likelihood of short sleep among SAs, whereas the presence of Cluster C PDs marginally diminished the probability of short sleep (Table 4).

--please insert **Table 4** about here--

In addition, short sleep duration did not differentiate between frequent SAs (defined as those SAs showing \geq 2 suicide attempts) and non-frequent SAs, even after stratifying by gender.

Third goal: studying the association of short sleep and suicide severity and risk

As for the association between short sleep and suicide severity and risk in SAs, we found significant associations only in the female SAs (Table 5), including several Becks' SIS item scores (items 12, 15, and A), and a score of \geq 3 in the SAD PERSONS scale; SIS Item C (Previous attempts) and Beck's Medical Lethality Scale (BMLS) were close to statistical significance (Table 5).

No association was found between short sleep and lethality of suicide attempts as measured by the RRRS in either gender. Furthermore, none of the four scales used to evaluate a putative relationship between short sleep and suicide severity and risk yielded any significant results in males, thus suggesting

that short sleep may not be associated with severity and risk of suicide attempts in males. Finally, in the logistic regression in the SAs with the SAD PERSONS score as the dependent variable, short sleep was very close to statistical significance (Wald chi [df=1]=2.91, p= 0.088), thus suggesting that the association between short sleep and the SAD PERSONS is, at least partly, independent from the effect of major depression and other variables.

--please insert **Table 5** about here--

Discussion

First goal: short sleep in cases and controls

The prevalence of short sleep by self-report in the adult US general population was 9.3% in 2006 (Knutson et al., 2010), which is virtually the same rate (9.2%) that we found in our healthy control sample. Unfortunately, the relationship of short sleep and suicidal behaviour is poorly studied. Our results offer new insights into this relationship. More than a third of SAs reported short sleep. Consistent with literature, short sleep was more likely to occur among SAs than psychiatric inpatients, suggesting that the role of short sleep is particularly important among patients showing suicidal behaviours. After reviewing the literature, Singareddy and Balon (2001) concluded that sleep disturbances are more frequent among psychiatric patients showing suicidal behaviour than among non-suicidal psychiatric patients. The seminal study by Fawcett et al. (1990) reached the same conclusion in depressive patients. Although the underlying mechanism that links short sleep and suicide is still not fully understood, it has been suggested that the impact of short sleep on the risk for suicide attempts may be explained by the

negative impact of cognitive functioning resulting in poor judgment, increases in impulsivity, tiredness and hopelessness (Goldstein, Bridge and Brent, 2008; Liu, 2004). In this regard, the results from our logistic regression analysis in the SA plus psychiatric control samples suggest that short sleep is significantly associated only with the diagnosis of current MDE and older age and not with having committed a suicide attempt.

Interestingly, the increased likelihood of short sleep among SAs when compared with psychiatric controls was explained by the male SA patients sub-sample. This might be partly explained by the differences in the distribution of Axis I disorders. Male SA patients were significantly more likely diagnosed with current MDE than their psychiatric counterparts, whereas no significant difference was observed between female SAs and psychiatric controls with regard to the presence of current MDE. In other words, it is possible that male SAs showed short sleep more frequently because they were acutely depressed.

Second goal: studying variables associated with short sleep in SAs

Univariate analyses showed that short sleep was significantly more frequent among male SAs. In the logistic regression, however, male gender was only marginally associated with short sleep in SAs. Our results suggest, therefore, that the association between male gender and suicide attempts may depend on the presence of current MDE. Unfortunately, in the few prior studies addressing the topic of sleep disturbances in SAs, the authors did not pay attention to gender issues (Sjostrom et al., 2007), thus making it more difficult to contrast our results.

As in the case of gender, the topic of age-related changes in sleep duration and quality remains unexplored in SAs. Although total time of sleep is considered to gradually decrease with age, the evidence is far from definitive (Klerman and Dijk, 2008; Monk et al., 2006; Ohayon et al., 2004). In our sample of SAs, older age was associated with an increased likelihood of short sleep in the univariate analyses. However, the logistic regression analyses failed to verify these results. Again, the association between short sleep and age in SAs might be a function of whether or not SAs are anxious or depressed.

In agreement with the literature, short sleep was associated with major depression and GAD (Monti & Monti, 2000). The relationship between short sleep and major depression and GAD in SAs is complex and the direction of causality between sleep disturbances and mood disorders is still unresolved (Agargun et al., 1997). The cross-sectional design of our study prevented us from implying any causality between short sleep time and suicide attempts. Sleep disturbance is a diagnostic criterion for major depression and GAD and insomnia is a frequent symptom in patients with major depression and GAD (Monti & Monti, 2000). In the Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety, major depressive disorder and anxiety disorders were linked with short sleep duration (van Mill et al., 2010). Recent reports, however, suggest that sleep disturbances might be specifically associated with suicidal behaviours (Bernert et al., 2005; Carli et al., 2010). Goodwin and Marusic (2008) reported that short sleep increased the likelihood of suicide attempts after controlling for antisocial PD and several Axis I disorders. Moreover, Liu reported that sleeping less than 8 hours/day increased the likelihood

for suicide attempts in adolescents after adjustment for demographic variables and depressive symptoms (Liu, 2004).

Interestingly, the presence of a Cluster C PD was marginally associated with decreased short sleep in SAs. Short sleep has been associated with neuroticism and self-criticism (Vincent et al., 2009), but evidence about a putative relationship between short sleep and PDs is missing. In addition, we did not find any significant association between short sleep and lifetime impulsivity as measured by the BIS. More research, however, is warranted to discard a potential link between sleep disturbances and personality dimensions. The effects between sleep disturbances and personality seem to be bidirectional (Soehner et al., 2007; Vincent et al., 2009). Future studies should assess personality and PDs as part of a group of factors that might be involved in the development of insomnia or other sleep disturbances among SAs.

Third goal: studying the association of short sleep and suicide risk

Short-sleep female SAs scored higher in some Beck's SIS items linked to greater severity of suicide attempts. Short sleep female SAs seriously attempted suicide, showed a higher degree of premeditation, and failed to criticize the suicide attempts more frequently than non-short-sleep female SAs. These results are in accordance with the greater percentage of short-sleep female attempters showing higher medical lethality (BMLS) and suicide risk (SAD PERSONS scale). Therefore, even if short sleep is not as frequent among females as among male SAs (see first goal comments), short sleep may be a marker of severity of suicidal behaviour in female attempters. In addition, our results are not explained by age, because female SAs were younger than their male counterparts, nor by the

presence of Axis I and II diagnoses because male SAs showed a more severe profile than female SAs. Therefore, short sleep SAs may deserve the implementation of specific suicide prevention measures (i.e., including questions with regard to sleep duration and quality), particularly in the case of females. Unfortunately, there is virtually no literature on the relationship between sleep duration and suicide intent, lethality and risk. Therefore, our results should be considered exploratory and deserve confirmation in a larger prospective study.

Strengths and Limitations

The major strengths of this study include the use of well-validated instruments to diagnose psychiatric and PDs and a large sample of SAs. Even so, larger samples may be needed to explore some of these issues using multivariate techniques; our results should be considered preliminary. Indeed, our major finding, that of a relationship between short sleep and different measures of severity of suicidal behaviour, should be confirmed in larger studies controlling for putative confounding variables (e.g., gender, age, depression).

There are also many other limitations. Firstly, sleep duration was not assessed with any standardized test; rather, total sleep time was assessed by self-report during in-depth psychiatric interviews. Therefore, the assessment of total sleep time is subject to retrospective bias that may be more severe among those who have experienced a suicide attempt. Secondly, our psychiatric controls did not include less severe cases of psychiatric disorders. It is likely that the prevalence of short sleep would be somewhat lower among outpatient samples. In any case, psychiatric populations can be quite heterogeneous in terms of specific sleep disturbances (e.g. bipolar patients in depressive phases often present atypical

symptoms with hypersomnia rather than insomnia). Therefore, our results might have been affected by the different distribution of mental disorders. Thirdly, we did not control for any medical condition or medications that the patients might be receiving. Nor did we control for the severity of mental disorders in the comparison of short sleep rates between SAs and psychiatric patients; therefore, any conclusions in this regard are highly speculative. Fourthly, the SAD PERSONS scale considers male sex and older age in its assessment, and this may have affected the association analyses between suicide risk and sex or age. However, the very fact that our analyses yielded significant results among female SAs who, in addition, were young and therefore less likely to score high on the SAD PERSONS scale, gives further support to our results in female SAs. Related to this, the observed associations with SAs might have been explained to at least some extent by severity of depression or psychiatric illness. Obviously, one might take suicide attempts as a priori evidence of more severe illness, leading to a kind of tautological problem. In any case, future studies should address this problem by controlling for severity of mental illness. Finally, the cross-sectional design of our study prevented us from drawing any conclusion about the sequence and timing between short sleep and other variables in SAs. Prospective follow-up studies are warranted to tackle the causality roles of major depression and short sleep in patients showing suicidal behaviours.

Conclusions

The results from this study provide novel insights into the relationship between short sleep duration and suicidal behaviour. Major depression and GAD increased the likelihood of short sleep among SAs. Male SAs more frequently reported short

sleep than female SAs. Even so, our most interesting finding was probably that of a relationship between short sleep and several measures of suicide severity and risk in female SAs. In other words, although male suicide attempters are more likely short sleepers, the presence of short sleep may be a marker of intent, severity and risk for suicidal behaviour among females. Our results stress the importance of implementing preventive measures among those at risk for suicidal behaviours. Early diagnosis and treatment of sleep disturbances in females might prevent the development of psychiatric disorders or ameliorate their symptoms (Ford and Kamerow, 1989; Monti and Monti, 2000), thus decreasing the risk of suicidal behaviours. Questions about sleep quality and duration should routinely be asked in every medical setting, but in the light of our findings, this recommendation seems particularly relevant for female SA patients. This simple measure may prove helpful in the prevalence and severity of suicide attempts among females.

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Conflict of interest: In the last 24 months, Dr. de Leon collaborated in an NIH grant in collaboration with GENOMAS. The remaining authors report no conflict of interest.

Contributors: Dr. Baca-Garcia designed the original studies and Drs. de Leon and Saiz-Ruiz contributed to the conception and design of the original studies. Dr. Blasco-Fontecilla proposed the hypothesis described in this study. Ms. Alegria and Legido-Gil and Dr. Lopez-Castroman helped with the complex work of getting the database ready for these analyses. Dr. Baca-Garcia conducted the statistical analyses with the help of Drs. Blasco-Fontecilla and de Leon. Dr. Blasco-Fontecilla wrote the first draft of the article with the help of Drs. Baca-Garcia and de Leon. All authors have contributed to and have approved the final manuscript.

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Table 1. Suicidal behaviour scales used in this study.

Scale	Suicide intent scale (SIS)	Risk-Rescue Rating Scale (RRRS)	Beck's Medical Lethality Scale (BMLS)	SAD PERSONS
Items	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Isolation 2. Timing 3. Precautions 4. Acting to get help 5. Final acts 6. Active preparation 7. Suicide note 8. Prior communication 9. Alleged purpose 10. Expectations of fatality 11. Conception of method 12. Seriousness of attempt 13. Attitude toward dying 14. Conception of rescuability 15. Degree of premeditation <p>A. Reaction to attempt B. Visualization of death C. Previous attempt</p>	<p>Risk factors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agent used 2. Impaired consciousness 3. Lesions/toxicity 4. Reversibility 5. Treatment required <p>Rescue factors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Location 2. Person initiation rescue 3. Probability of discovery by any rescuer 4. Accessibility to rescue 5. Delay until discovery 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Fully conscious 8. Death 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sex: Male 2. Age: Old 3. Depression 4. Previous attempt 5. Ethanol abuse 6. Rational thinking loss 7. Lack of Social supports 8. Organized plan 9. No Spouse 10. Sickness
Item Scores (Global scale score)	0-2 (0-30)*	1-3 (10-30)**	(0-8)□	1 each item (0-10)□ □

* The SIS has 15 items rated 0 to 2, and some other issues (Item A, B, and C) not included in the global score (Misson et al., 2010).

High risk: >16.3 and low risk: <6.7

** High risk: 13-15; Low rescuability: 14-15

+ The Beck's Medical Lethality Scale (BMLS) is a Likert scale of 0–8 (fully conscious – death). The BMLS threshold for hospitalization for treatment of the medical consequences is considered to be 4. As suggested in the literature, suicide attempts

scored 4 and higher were considered to be high lethality attempts and those with scores between 0 and 3 were considered low lethality attempts (Beck et al., 1975; Zalsman et al., 2006).

†† A score of 0-2 indicates little risk, of 3-4 to follow the patient closely, of 5-6 to strongly consider hospitalization, and of 7-10 very high risk of suicide indicating hospitalization. In our sample, few SAs scored ≥ 5 ; therefore, we considered a high score ≥ 3 .

Table 2. Prevalence of MINI diagnoses among suicide attempters and psychiatric inpatients.

	Women			Men			Total		
	Suicide attempters (N=287)	Psychiatric inpatients (N=45)	Significance (Fisher Exact Test, FET)	Suicide attempters (N=141)	Psychiatric inpatients (N=31)	Significance (FET)	Suicide attempters (N=428)	Psychiatric inpatients (N=83)	Significance (FET)
Current major depressive episode (MDE)	55%	44%	ns	63%	32%	p=0.002	58%	40%	p=0.004
Past MDE	28%	10%	p=0.016	40%	10%	p=0.008	32%	10%	p<0.001
Current dysthymia	12%	11%	ns	5%	0.0%	ns	10%	7%	ns
Current manic episode	0%	2%	ns	1%	0.0%	ns	0%	1%	ns
Past manic episode	3%	0%	ns	3%	ns	ns	3%	0%	ns
Current hypomanic episode	1%	0%	ns	0%	0%	ns	0%	0%	ns
Past hypomanic episode	5%	0%	ns	6%	0%	ns	5%	0%	p=0.034
Current panic disorder	9%	31%	p<0.001	7%	23%	p=0.016	8%	28%	p<0.001
Lifetime panic disorder	7%	12%	ns	4%	3%	ns	6%	9%	ns
Current agoraphobia	6%	2%	ns	3%	0%	p=0.028	5%	1%	p=0.028
Current social phobia	9%	2%	ns	7%	7%	ns	8%	4%	ns
Current OCD	4%	6%	ns	1%	7%	ns	3%	6%	ns
Alcohol dependence (past 12 months)	7%	0%	p=0.054	24%	23%	ns	13%	8%	ns
Alcohol abuse (past 12 months)	8%	0%	p=0.033	18%	3%	p=0.051	11%	1%	p=0.03
Substance dependence (past 12 months)	4%	0%	ns	16%	6%	ns	8%	2%	ns
Substance abuse (past 12 months)	4%	0%	ns	9%	3%	ns	6%	1%	ns
Current psychotic disorders	3%	0%	ns	4%	3%	ns	3%	1%	ns
Lifetime psychotic disorders	4%	0%	ns	8%	7%	ns	6%	2%	ns
Current anorexia nervosa	4%	0%	ns	1%	0%	ns	3%	0%	ns
Current bulimia nervosa	9%	0%	p=0.035	1%	0%	ns	6%	0%	p=0.023
Current generalized anxiety disorder	19%	33%	p=0.040	13%	23%	ns	17%	29%	p=0.015

Table 3. Prevalence of short sleep duration in suicide attempters, psychiatric controls and healthy controls stratified by gender.

	Suicide attempters	Psychiatric controls	OR (CI) ¹	Healthy controls	OR (CI) ²
Total sample	37% (159/434)	23% (19/83)	2.0 (1.1-3.4) ³	9% (47/509)	5.7 (4.0-8.1) ³
Females	33% (95/289)	33% (17/52)	1.01(0.5-1.9)	7% (14/201)	11.5 (2.6-49.8) ³
Males	44% (64/145)	7% (2/31)	6.5 (3.6-11.9) ³	11% (33/308)	6.6 (4.0-10.7) ³

OR: odds ratio. CI: confidence interval.

¹ OR between suicide attempters and psychiatric controls

² OR between suicide attempters and healthy controls

³ Fisher exact test (FET): p<0.001

Table 4. Variables significantly associated with short sleep in univariate and logistic regression analyses within suicide attempters (n=434)

Variable	Univariate Analyses OR (CI)	Logistic regression ¹ OR (CI)
Age	□	#
Gender (male)	1.6 (1-2.4)**	#
MDE (current)	2.6 (1.7-3.9)*	2.6 (1.6-4.1)*
GAD	1.9 (1.1-3.1)**	1.8 (1.0-3.3)**
Cluster B PDS	0.7 (0.5-1)	#
Cluster C PDS	0.7 (0.4-1)	0.6 (0.3-0.9)**

OR: odds ratio. CI: confidence interval. MDE: major depressive episode.

GAD: general anxiety disorder. PDS: personality disorders.

¹The Hosmer and Lemeshow Test significance was 0.141

□ Risk estimate statistics could not be computed. They are only computed for a 2*2 table. The distribution of short sleep among SAs is as follows: 18-35 yo (30%); 36-50 yo (41%); 51-65 yo (40%); >65 (59%); p=0.012

Blank spaces in logistic regression indicated non-significant ORs

* P <0.001

** P <0.05

Table 5. Suicide severity and risk scale variables associated with short sleep in female suicide attempters.

Clinical variables *		Short sleep	Non-short sleep	p value (2-sided)
SIS ITEM 12 (Seriousness)	Did not seriously attempt to end life	13%	22%	0.041
	Uncertain about seriousness to end life	33%	40%	
	Seriously attempted to end life	54%	39%	
SIS ITEM 15 (Degree of premeditation)	None; impulsive	59%	65%	0.016
	Suicide contemplated for three hours or less prior to attempt	10%	17%	
	Suicide contemplated for more than three hours prior to attempt	31%	17%	
SIS ITEM A (Reaction to attempt)	Sorry it was made: feel foolish; ashamed	43%	55%	0.039
	Accepts both attempt and failure	20%	22%	
	Regrets failure of attempt	37%	23%	
SAD PERSONS	0-2 (little risk)	44%	66%	0.003
	≥3 (at least following patient closely)	56%	34%	

SIS: Suicide Intent Scale.

* SIS Item C (Previous attempts) and Beck's Medical Lethality Scale (BMLS) were close to statistical significance (p=0.053 and p=0.056, respectively)